

Exploring Dependencies of Networks of Multi-Genre Network Experiments

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Abstract—Tactical networks are modeled using multi-genre networks, a composition of communication, information and social networks. These networks are designed to support the soldier to maintain situation awareness in extreme network environments. We present initial steps to enabling the study of parameters of a multi-genre network and the impact they have on other layers as well as global mission performance metrics. The framework in this paper provides experimental results of a multi-genre network consisting of EMANE, a communications network emulation platform and ELICIT, a command and control experiment platform that represents the social network layer. With these, we explore several parameters of the framework to demonstrate the impact of one parameter on the performance of other layers of the network. As a result, we are able to gain insight into enhancing performance of such networks. We are able to see initial results in terms of the impact of parameters between network layers and on the global network performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tactical networks can be modeled by the composition of communication, information and social networks. Using this approach, one is able to study the relationships between and among the various network layers, gaining insight into aspects of tactical networks that were previously unable to be understood. Previous to network science research for military networks, traditional approaches considered single layers of the network, primarily focusing on the communication network. If a satisfactory bandwidth was provided, then the network was considered to be providing sufficient service. However, given the expanding connectedness of military networks, it is necessary to understand the impact of aspects of this network model. This will provide a holistic approach to military networks and enhance mission performance beyond its current state. Further, while theory and models are being developed, there is even less in the way of experimental capabilities. We present a novel experiment framework that allows for the testing of the multi-genre characterization of tactical networks.

Network science research for military networks has adopted the multi-genre network as a fundamental building block to represent tactical networks [1]. Each node in this multi-genre network is a node on each network layer and we assume that intra-layer links exist between the node and each network layer (e.g., communication, information, social) on which it exists. Each of the network layers maintains its own topology/connectivity. Given these intricate relationships, there is little in terms of the fundamental understanding of these networks both theoretically and empirically. Validation of novel multi-genre network theories is important and is a key

component to the realization of providing improved network capabilities to edge users.

Experimentation on multi-genre networks has been an ongoing research effort, with particular interest for Army tactical networks. In this paper we address the implementation challenges involved in developing experiment platforms for multi-genre networks. Existing network experiment platforms generally treat individual network layers, only allowing for the exploration of parameters in one layer. Further, integrating multiple experiment platforms faces many technical issues in terms of interoperability, even if it was determined that the platforms were compatible in theory. Our past work has developed a network shim layer that provides a transport layer between platforms that enables communications between the platforms. Initial efforts to combine communications and social networks were done using ELICIT and EMANE [2], but the most recent approach makes use of a generalized shim layer design that enables other experiment platforms to be inserted into the framework given the demands and advances of research [3].

As an initial effort to validate the viability of this platform, we devised a source selection scenario to gathered elements from various layers of the multi-genre network and evaluated the quality of a set of sources based on the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) [4]. However, portions of the data for these experiments were synthetic and collected in separate experiments. In this paper, we conducted experiments and gathered measurements from a single experiment. Our recent advancement in dynamic virtualization facilitated the execution of the experiments, allowing for multiple experiments to be simultaneously run [5].

II. RELATED WORK

This work is part of a large effort of network science research for military networks. These experimental developments are relatively unique for the type of multi-genre networks we are considering.

There is a long history of multi-layer network experiments in the communications network domain [6], but are not capturing behavior of the breadth of networks in the tactical domain. There is ongoing work on multiteam systems [7], investigating the dynamics of various communication patterns and interactions. However, the treatment of communications patterns is still more social than communications. Similar interoperability issues were experienced in live, virtual, constructive for network centric operations activities [8].

In terms of quality of information, there is existing work in terms of value of information [9] consider the value of information from multiple sources to derive strategies to fuse information. There is also past work on AHP formulation for the Quality of Information (QoI) versus Value of Information (VoI)[10]. This work builds on the recent literature by providing an experimentation framework to conduct experiments with high fidelity and sophistication.

III. ARCHITECTURE/Framework

Our framework includes multiple experiment platforms of existing experiments that studied a subset of the multi-genre network stack. To demonstrate the feasibility of this framework, it consists of a command and control experiment platform *ELICIT*, a network emulation platform *EMANE*. We also make use of a shim layer that performs the message translation and communication among the various platforms. We note that it is possible to integrate other experimental platforms to this framework.

A. *ELICIT*

The Experimental Laboratory for Investigating Collaboration, Information-sharing, and Trust (*ELICIT*) is a command and control experiment platform that was initially designed to study various command and control concepts relating to organizational design and team composition. First used as a web-based human-in-the-loop experiment platform, sensemaking agents were designed to conduct experiments, enabling the execution of large scale simulations. This allowed for the possibility for multi-genre network experiments to include this aspect of C2 experiments. An initial investigation into the merging of communications and social networks was studied in past work [2].

The setup of *ELICIT* was for a group of individuals (or agents) to be connected according to various command and control organizational structure. The initial investigations considered hierarchical and edge topologies. Originally designed for 17 individuals consisting of a cross team coordinator, 4 team leads, who each had 4 team members. In the edge structure, each individual could communicate with every other individual. In this work, we consider a simplified model of 4 agents with one team leader as the analyst and 3 team members as information sources. We use both the edge and hierarchy C2 approaches in these experiments.

The goal of the organization is to determine the “who”, “what”, “where”, and “when” of a fictitious insurgent threat by aggregating a set of information, called factoids. Each agent is given a subset of this information at the start of the experiment. With this information each agent is unable to solve the problem, but by combining this information, it is possible. The factoid categories are: Expert, Key, Support and Noise. The factoids exist in natural language or encoded for the software agents. At the start of the experiment, the factoids are distributed and then the agents *SHARE* factoids with other agents. They perform sensemaking on the factoids

they receive, and then once they solve some portion of the problem they submit an *IDENTIFY*.

ELICIT can be measured by several aspects of the performance of the organization specific to the social network. The performance of the group is determined by the completeness of the sub problems that predetermined decision makers have solved by the end of the experiment. In terms of mission performance, it can be measured by the time to first correct, “First Correct Id time”. That is, the time of the experiment at which an agent is able to submit a completely correct *IDENTIFY*. The runs were 60 minutes in duration. To measure the efficiency of the configuration of the organization, we also monitor the number of packets or *SHAREs* transmitted throughout the course of the experiment.

One limitation of this platform is the immediate sharing and perfect transmission of the factoids between agents. To enhance the realism of the experiments, we propose to add more realistic communications between the agents, here, done through network emulation.

B. *CORE/EMANE*

Network emulation introduces realistic tactical communications behavior into application testing environments, and in general provides a balanced alternative to intractable and unrepeatable network field tests and low fidelity network simulation testing. The Common Open Research Emulator (*CORE*) and Extendable Mobile Ad-hoc Network Emulator (*EMANE*) were incorporated into the framework to add a higher level of realism by modeling the imperfect and constrained transmission layer between the *ELICIT* agents. *CORE* provides a way to easily configure testbed networking through Linux *LXC* Container virtualization and network namespacing, a technique that instantiates multiple instances of network interfaces and routing tables within a single OS. *EMANE* handles real-time modeling of OSI Layers 1 and 2 connectivity via pluggable MAC and PHY implementations that model signal propagation, interference and antennae profile effects.

Each virtual container created within the *CORE* emulation environment runs an independent instance of the *ELICIT* agent software on top of its own complete network stack with communications links to the other participating agents. Factoid messages shared between agents via these communications links were subjected to propagation effects modeled by *EMANE*, specifically its RF-Pipe radio waveform. The RF-Pipe radio model exposes various configurable parameters such as transmission datarate, packet delay, jitter and bandwidth, all of which can be tuned to create a variety of radio waveforms. As an emulation environment, it is possible to monitor the message and packet transmissions over time, packet latency and other network statistics. Typically the *ELICIT* platform runs in an environment with near perfect communications where bandwidth resources are in excess, quite the opposite of tactical networks. Therefore we modeled the *CORE/EMANE* emulated networking environment with radio waveforms covering a varying range of datarates and bandwidths as shown in Table I.

C. Shim

To enable communications between ELICIT and the EMANE emulated network layers, we designed a network shim [3]. The Shim interface is a messaging bus where customized messages can be exchanged between the various platform components via the emulated communications network. It uses a stack model, where messages are sent to different components in the stack linearly for processing before being sent over the emulated network. The Shim was also designed to allow modules to be swapped in and out to test different phenomena, thus allowing for a wide range of different experimentation deployments to be run. Figure 1 illustrates the deployment used for our experimentation and shows how Factoid messages are exchanged between ELICIT agents using the Shim. First the Factoid message traverses down the stack from the sending ELICIT agent, next it is transmitted through the EMANE emulated network, and finally back up the stack to the receiving ELICIT agent.

Fig. 1: Architecture of Shim for Network Framework

IV. EXPERIMENT DESIGN

To demonstrate the multi-genre network experiment approach, we consider a source selection application for tactical networked environments. In this scenario, an analyst is tasked with an information gathering activity and must pull information from a set of sources, aggregate and perform sensemaking on this information to attain situation understanding. Our example scenario consists of the analyst and three sources. The intelligence activity is represented by ELICIT and the communications are done over CORE/EMANE.

To further enhance the realism of these experiments, we conducted experiments over a wide range of parameters of the experiment framework. These parameters are drawn from

various levels of the multigenre network representation. These parameters, the values used and the layer from which they were taken are shown in Table I. For the communications layer, we varied the bandwidth over a range of 4 kbps to 50 kbps, where beyond this data rate, no discernible performance difference was observed. For the information layer, we modified the distribution of factoids to be *randomly* distributed and *assigned* such that each node had all of the Expert, Key, and Support factoids. We also varied the amount of noise in the factoid set, which contained {0 (Low), 17 (Medium), 34 (High)} factoids with no value to solving the task. We also varied the size of the factoids, to represent the communication of various media such as text (in the order of kilobytes), images (kb - Mb) or video clips (10 Mb - 100 Mb). In our experiments, we consider the uniform case where all of the factoid sizes were the same {5kb, 10kb, 5Mb, 10Mb}. We also used a non-uniform factoid size case, where we set the size of the factoids for each information value: {Expert: 50kb, Key: 500kb, Support: 20kb, Noise: 20kb}. On the social network layer, we varied the C2 approach to be either hierarchical or edge. This set of experiments enables us to explore the multi-genre network and the impact of one network parameter on the global performance of the network.

Fig. 2: Diagram of Experimentation workflow of ELICIT messages being sent to the appropriate ELICIT agents.

The experimentation workflow illustrated in Figs 2 and 3 is summarized in the following:

- 1) The ELICIT Server generates factoid messages and sends them via the local network to the appropriate ELICIT Agents according to the distribution scheme.
- 2) When an ELICIT Agent decides to share a factoid the Agent sends a message to the Shim and places the Factoid into a queue.
- 3) The Shim, upon receiving a message from an ELICIT Agent, generates a packet of pre-calculated size depend-

Fig. 3: Diagram of Experimentation workflow of ELICIT messages showing flow of message through ELICIT, CORE and Shim layer (Steps 1 - 7).

Parameter	Range	Network Layer
Bandwidth	4kbps - 50kbps	Communication
Factoid distribution	random, assigned	Comms/Info
Factoid size	uniform, non-uniform	Information
Noise level	high, medium, low	Information
Organization	hierarchy, edge	Social

TABLE I: multi-genre network parameters with range or set of values and their corresponding network layer represented

ing on the factoid category and sends the packet to the corresponding agent via EMANE.

- 4) EMANE calculates the path loss and propagates the packet through the emulated network to the corresponding ELICIT Agent with whom the Factoid is being shared.
- 5) The packet is delivered via EMANE to the corresponding ELICIT Agent and delivered up the stack to the corresponding Shim.
- 6) The Shim on the receiving nodes receives the packet and sends a notification to the ELICIT Server that the packet has arrived.
- 7) The ELICIT Server receives the notification and releases the queued factoid to the appropriate ELICIT Agent and records that the factoid has been shared.

This process continues for 3 rounds of factoids distributions each occurring at designated times during the experiment. Once the factoids are received by the ELICIT Agents they can attempt to identify the “who”, “what”, “where”, and “when” of the insurgent threat. This continues until the end of designated set experimental time.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The initial experimental results demonstrate the feasibility of this experiment framework. Further, we are able to see the impact of different network layer parameters and their impact on the task performance. We show results for several metrics of the multi-genre network used for source selection.

First, we show results for the number of packets received over EMANE and the number of SHARES received in ELICIT. This allows us to see the impact of variable bandwidth and the performance of the communication layer and information layers. Then, we show the “First Correct Id Time” as a function of the available bandwidth. This captures the relationship between the social network and the rest of the network layers. We provide results for the baseline configurations of edge and hierarchical C2 approaches using uniform or non-uniform factoid sizes.

As a ‘baseline’ configuration, we present results for uniform factoid size with low noise. For low noise, small factoid size and high bandwidth, we expect the mission solution time to be the lowest. Any other configuration would be sub-optimal. As can be seen in Fig. 4, the lowest factoid size indeed reflects the quickest solution time. Also, we observe some minimum bandwidth required for any packets to be successfully transmitted. We see difficulty in the high factoid size to be successfully transmitted in ELICIT, which is also reflected in Fig. 4a. There is a general trend that as the bandwidth increases, the number of packets received decreases.

A key aspect of C2 experiments is the performance of different organizations or approaches. We show the same configuration as Figs. 6 and 7 for the edge organization. We see similar tendencies with the shares received as a function of factoid size, but we see that for moderately large factoids, that the number of shares increases steadily, rather than saturating quickly. In terms of EMANE received packets, similar trends are observed, while the saturation as bandwidth increases is slightly less pronounced than compared with the hierarchical plots. More specifically, as the size of the factoid increases to 10Mb, the number of packets sent in EMANE do not drastically increase; nor do the number of shares diminish significantly in relation to being a factor of 1000 times larger than the 10kb packet size. This seems to signify that there is a range between 10kb and 10Mb where increasing the size of the packets (communications) does not impact the number of shares transmitted (social). This is evidence of the network bandwidth not being fully utilized. We will look at saturation behavior to be future work.

Fig. 8 shows the same network metrics for the case where the factoid sizes are non-uniform for the three levels of noise in the factoids. We observe that after some bandwidth threshold, the number of ELICIT shares saturates, while the number of EMANE packets received tend to decrease as bandwidth is increased. We observe that this may be a result of lower packet drops thus less retransmissions. Additionally, in Fig. 9, we see a relatively monotonic behavior with regard to bandwidth. As bandwidth increases, solution times decrease. The experimental results are for a single run, with additional runs, it is expected that the artifacts due to a dropped packet or agent decision that produced non-monotonic results would be suppressed. As the noise increases, we see general trends that the solution time increases. Also, due to the non-uniformity of the factoids, we see that for a single run, there are cases where the solution is not obtained (e.g., distMR). So, in this case

(a)

(a)

(b)

(b)

Fig. 4: Number of successful packets received (a) and successful shares received (b) vs available bandwidth for hierarchical organization, uniform factoid size (last legend detail) for low noise level (first letter after dist) and random or assigned factoid distribution (second letter after dist).

Fig. 6: Number of successful packets received (a) and successful shares received (b) vs available bandwidth for edge organization, non-uniform factoid size for low noise level (first letter after dist) and random or assigned factoid distribution (second letter after dist).

Fig. 5: First Correct Id time vs. bandwidth for hierarchical organization, non-uniform factoid size for low noise and random and assigned factoid distribution (second letter after dist).

there appears to be greater variability in the solution times.

With these experimental results, we are able to obtain initial insight into the impact that behavior of one network layer has on the others. We can look into the dynamics between the communications and information networks as shown in Figs 6a and 6b. At 20 kbps, we can see that doubling

the factoid packet size from 5kb to 10kb in the low noise random factoid assignment case results in a 35% increase in packets received in EMANE and impacts the total number of achievable shares in ELICIT, reducing it by 61%. This highlights the implications of using different media types, on the network traffic incurred, and then the on sharing behavior on the social layer, which has a direct impact of the decision-making ability of the analyst.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have presented a framework that enables the execution of multi-genre network experiments involving social, information and communication networks. We have explored various parameters in the network space and through an integrated simulation platform using ELICIT, EMANE and CORE, and other experimental capabilities, we are able to provide new insight into the interactions of different network layers and the impact they may have on the end user performance of a source selection task. Our platform enabled us

Fig. 7: First Correct Id time vs. bandwidth for edge organization, non-uniform factoid size for high, medium and low noise level (first letter after dist) and random or assigned factoid distribution (second letter after dist).

Fig. 9: First Correct Id time vs. bandwidth for hierarchical organization, non-uniform factoid size for low noise level (first letter after dist) and random and assigned factoid distribution (second letter after dist).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8: Number of successful packets received (a) and successful shares received (b) vs available bandwidth for hierarchical organization, non-uniform factoid size for the three levels of factoid noise level.

to gather behavior from different layers of the multi-genre network and combine these behavior estimates to enhance our understanding of the network state from a multi-genre network perspective. We established a baseline result of the organization with regard to bandwidth, information distribution and organizational approach, then we explored the parameter space to understand the impact of these parameters through

simulation. This provides the network designer with insight on predicted organizational performance and also allows for optimization of network performance through campaigns of missions.

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